

Integrating Technology in Primary Curriculum Development: Improving the Quality of Education

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the importance of technology integration in developing elementary school (SD) curricula to improve the quality of education. The strategy for improving the quality of education is to implement information technology in school learning. This implementation will support the learning process which produces students skilled in anticipating advances in science and technology. The method used in this study uses a library research method or approach, library research can be interpreted as a series of activities relating to methods of collecting library data, reading and recording and processing research materials

INTRODUCTION

In general, technology is a whole means of providing goods necessary for the continuity and comfort of human life. Human use of technology begins with changing natural resources into simple tools. Technology in education is very important to support the development of education for the better (Purba, et al. 2020). In the world of education, technology can be used to facilitate the learning process, such as using e-learning, video conferencing, or interactive learning applications. With technology, the information needed will be faster and easier to access for educational purposes, such as in curriculum development.

The curriculum is a set or system of plans and arrangements regarding learning materials that can be guided in teaching and learning activities. The curriculum is a guideline in determining the direction to achieve educational goals in each educational unit which has been prepared by each educational unit which is known as the educational unit level curriculum (Hakim, 2017).

Education is a planned basic effort to create a learning atmosphere and learning process so that students actively develop their potential to have religious spiritual strength (Pristiwanti, et al. 2022). Through education, a capable, skilled and knowledgeable human being will be created as a provision for life in the future, and able to live independently amidst the current rapid advances in technological science. The educational process will run well if the tools applied in an educational institution are implemented properly so that it will produce human resources who have integrity and are able to compete in the wider world. For this reason, it is necessary to integrate technology to help develop a better curriculum so that the goals of education itself can be achieved.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Education is one of the main foundations in the development of society. In today's digital era, integrating technology in the development of elementary school curriculum is crucial. This is not only to keep up with the times, but also to improve the quality of education. So in this article, we will explore how technology can help maximize the elementary curriculum, provide a more engaging learning experience, and improve student understanding and achievement. Thus, technology integration is not just an option, but an urgent need in efforts to improve the quality of education in elementary schools.

The development of the times and technology is increasing, thus bringing about changes in human life. Seeing the fact that information and communication technology is not just a complementary human tool but has become a basic part of human life.

The development of information technology that is increasingly rapid in the era of globalization can no longer be avoided anymore influence on the world of education. Changes in the learning process are needed to make updates in accordance with the dynamics of the increasingly rapid development (Muali et al., 2018). Global demands demand that the world of education always adapt technological developments to efforts to improve the quality of education, one of which is through the application of technology information in learning to improve the quality of students.

METHODOLOGY

The method used in this study uses a library research method or approach, library research can be interpreted as a series of activities related to methods of collecting library data, reading and taking notes as well as processing research materials (Zed, 2008) and library research at least There are four main characteristics that writers need to pay attention to, including: first, that the writer or researcher is dealing directly with text (Nash) or numerical data, not with direct knowledge from the field. Second, library data is "ready to use" meaning that the researcher does not go directly into the field because the researcher is dealing directly with data sources in the library. Third, that library data is generally a secondary source, in the sense that researchers obtain material or data from second hand and not original data from first hand data in the field. Fourth, that the condition of library data is not limited by space and time (Zed, 2008) based on the above, data collection in research is carried out by reviewing and/or exploring several journals, books and documents (both printed and electronic) as well as other sources of data or information that are considered relevant to the research or study

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Basic education (SD) is a critical stage in forming the foundation of children's knowledge and skills. In the digital era that continues to develop, integrating technology into the elementary school curriculum has become a necessity to improve the quality of education. This is why educators and policy makers must understand the important role of technology in developing an effective elementary school curriculum (Sa'ud, et al. 2007).

Human use of technology begins with changing natural resources into simple tools. Technology in education is very important to support the development of education for the better. In the world of education, technology can be used to facilitate the learning process, such as using e-learning, video conferencing, or interactive learning applications (Lestari. 2018). With technology, the information needed will be faster and easier to access for educational purposes, such as in curriculum development.

The use of technology in elementary school curriculum development not only allows for more interesting and interactive learning but can also improve student learning outcomes. The following are several ways that integrating technology can improve the quality of education in elementary schools:

- Access online learning resources. Technology allows students to access online learning resources, such as learning videos, simulations and interactive modules. This provides a more varied and interesting learning experience.
- Personalize learning. With technology, teachers can adapt learning to suit the individual needs of each student. Adaptive learning applications can help identify student weaknesses and provide appropriate material.
- Collaboration and communication. Technology facilitates collaboration between students and teachers, even between students. This helps improve students' social and collaborative skills, which are important competencies in the modern world.

- **Monitoring and evaluation.** Learning management systems allow teachers to track student progress more efficiently. This allows identifying problems early and providing appropriate interventions.
- **Real-time curriculum progress.** With technology, the curriculum can be updated quickly in accordance with developments in science and community needs, so that students receive relevant education.
- **Digital Skills Development.** Integrating technology helps students develop important digital skills for the 21st century. This equips them for an increasingly connected future.

Technology Integration in the Curriculum

Technology integration in the curriculum is not only about the use of technological devices in the classroom, but also about how technology can be used to improve students' understanding of subject matter (Suprayekti, 2011). Technology can be used to make learning material more interesting and interactive, such as through the use of multimedia, learning applications and online learning platforms.

The integration of technology in the curriculum is an essential approach in modern education. By integrating technology into the learning process, teachers can create a more engaging and effective learning experience for students. Technology allows wider access to educational resources, such as e-books, learning videos and other resources (Widodo, et al. 2023).

Apart from that, technology also allows for project-based learning, where students can develop practical skills while understanding the concepts in their lessons. The use of educational software and digital tools such as interactive boards can also increase student participation in class.

However, technology integration in synchronization also requires careful planning. Teachers must ensure that technology is used appropriately and is relevant to learning objectives. In addition, there needs to be attention to ethical safety in the use of technology in the classroom.

Overall, the integration of technology in the curriculum has great potential to improve the quality of education by providing more diverse and relevant learning experiences for students. In an increasingly connected world, the use of technology in learning is a must.

In addition, technology integration can also help students develop skills relevant for the 21st century, such as problem solving, creativity, critical thinking, and digital literacy. The ability to adapt to changing technology and work with digital tools is an invaluable skill in the modern world of work. In the context of the curriculum, teachers must also consider how technology can be used to measure and share student progress. Online learning management systems can help in tracking analysis and learning data, so teachers can provide more targeted feedback to students. However, it is important to remember that technology is not a magic solution to all challenges in education.

Technology integration must be based on clear and relevant learning objectives, teachers must continue to develop their skills in integrating technology effectively and ensure that all students have equal access to the necessary tools and resources. With careful planning and a commitment to optimizing the potential of technology, the integration of technology in the curriculum can change the way we teach and learn, creating a generation of students who are better prepared to face an ever-changing world. This is an important step towards a more connected and competitive future evolution of education.

Benefits of Technology Integration in the Curriculum

The use of technology in education has many benefits, namely:

- Technology can help teachers deliver lesson material more effectively. Teachers can utilize digital tools to explain concepts visually and interactively, helping students understand the material better.
- Technology can help students in the learning process by providing various learning resources that can be accessed anytime and anywhere, exploring topics that interest them, and accessing various supporting resources.
- Technology can help in assessing and evaluating student learning processes. Teachers can use special software to measure student progress, identify areas for improvement, and provide more precise feedback. In addition, technology also allows for more dynamic curriculum development, with the ability to update teaching materials and methods more appropriately.

By integrating technology into the curriculum, education can become more adaptive, interactive, and relevant to the demands of the modern world. This provides an opportunity for students to develop digital skills that are important in today's digital era. Thus, the benefits of technology integration in education are enormous.

Information Technology-Based Assessment

The development of information and communication technology, which is increasingly soaring as it is today, is being used by a number of educational activists to start directing exams or tests from traditional systems to move to computerized systems in order to improve the quality of education. Therefore, technological media needs to be used as a support in the process of assessing student learning outcomes, because so far teachers have carried out assessments of students using conventional methods, namely paper-based tests.

According to Munir (2008), several benefits that can be derived from the use of ICT include: a) computers can carry out work in a short time, b) can carry out repetitive work consistently, c) can carry out work precisely and minimize human error, d) with speed and consistency and accuracy, it can be estimated that the decisions produced can be trusted so that the same results can be obtained repeatedly, e) increase productivity and creativity (Sutrisno, 2012).

Assessment of learning outcomes by utilizing ICT can provide various conveniences in the process. Below are several examples of applications that can be used to create questions online:

a. Google Forms

The Google Form application is the first recommendation used to create online questions, which can be directly connected to Google's online learning application, namely Google Classroom. This application is free so it's free to use, so you just have to adjust it if you want to make online exam questions. This application can be used to create questions in the form of multiple choice, long or short essays. Apart from being used to create questions, this application is also used to create surveys and questionnaires to find out how effective the material presented is

b. Quizizz

Quizizz offers more interesting features than the others, namely having a more colorful display with interesting animations so that students don't get bored easily. We can also add background to make the exam more interesting. Quizizz has provided a bank of questions taken from other users, so we just have to look for the right material. There is also an online test feature that can be done in real time and then closed immediately or provides a grace period for processing.

c. ProProfs

This application has an interesting feature, so that after students do online exam questions, students will get the results of their work in the form of a certificate/charter with the grades achieved. However, the free version can only be used for 10 students, if more than that it is necessary to upgrade to the paid version.

d. QuizStar

This application is usually run through a website with question creation features, student administration, automatic assessment, and question features in multimedia form. The QuizStar application is completely free and we are free to use it. (Azam Arifin, 2020).

Through these various applications, the process of assessing student learning outcomes can be carried out without using paper (paperless) so that it can save costs for procuring questions, be economical, practical, easy, environmentally friendly, accurate and efficient.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Education is one of the main foundations in the development of society. In today's digital era, integrating technology in the development of elementary school curriculum is crucial. This is not only to keep up with the times, but also to improve the quality of education.

The curriculum is a set or system of plans and arrangements regarding learning materials that can be guided in teaching and learning activities. The use of technology in elementary school curriculum development not only allows for more interesting and interactive learning but can also improve student learning outcomes.

By utilizing technology, the teaching and learning process can become more interactive, interesting and effective. However, there needs to be adequate training and support for teachers to be able to make maximum use of this technology. Apart from that, there needs to be policies and regulations that support the use of technology in education

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations, so it is necessary to carry out further research related to the topic of Integrating Technology in Primary Curriculum Development: Improving the Quality of Education in order to improve this research and add insight to readers.

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